

Principals' Supervisory Techniques for Combating Corruption and the Attainment of Quality School Governance in Public Secondary Schools in Aba Education Zone of Abia State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated principals' supervisory techniques for combating corruption and the attainment of quality school governance. Two null hypotheses were formulated. The ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. Census technique was used to draw the entire population of 81 principals from all the public secondary schools in Aba Education Zone of Abia State. Data collection was carried out with the use of a research instrument titled: "Principals' Supervisory Techniques for Combating Corruption and Attainment of Quality School Governance Questionnaire (PSTCCAQSGQ)". The instrument was validated by two experts of Test and Measurement in the Department of Educational Foundations, University of Calabar. The reliability value obtained was .88 using Cronbach Alpha technique. One-way analysis of variance was used in testing the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Findings revealed that there is a significant influence of principals' clinical and demonstration techniques of supervision for combating corruption on quality school governance. Based on the findings, it was concluded that school governance should be enhanced with supervisory techniques by principals for the attainment of anti-corruption culture in Aba education zone of Abia State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Supervisory techniques, Corruption, Combating corruption, School governance, clinical techniques, Secondary schools.

Introduction

Globally, many educational institutions have witnessed poor supervision and pitiable governance, corruption, cultism, incessant increase in tuition fees, lack of management paying attention to student's complaints and welfare services, making unnecessary promises to students and not fulfilling them, campus terrorism, poor communication between the management and the students over stipulated increase in charges. Others are non-inclusion of student's in decision making, changing values systems of students, contemporary national issues and welfare problem (Falua, 2004). All these at various times had led to the loss of human lives and destruction of properties beyond estimation, the breakdown of law and order, delay in the time frame a student ought to spend in programme thereby spending more than the stipulated year of study.

To this effect, Ogonor (2013) aptly submitted that poor school governance and supervision has led to the proliferation of weapon and natured the culture of war and violence other than peace and security. This situation has hampered peace, growth, and as well, retarded national development in various countries such as South Africa, Somalia, North Korea to mention but a few. In Nigerian tertiary institutions, the trend is the same. The frequent occurrence of student crises in Nigerian institutions has been a matter of concern to educationists and stakeholders. Common observation shows that the country has witnessed a series of outbreaks of ethnic violence, terrorism religious extremism, dehumanization and school violence. The purpose of this paper is therefore to determine principals' supervisory

practices for combating corruption and its roles as an asset to curb poor governance and corruption in Nigerian secondary schools generally and Abia State in particular.

Quality school governance involves effective educational supervision to ensure access, equality, and accountability for goals attainment. These goals could be achieved in secondary schools through high-level manpower training. Such training provides accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities for all students despite their gender, social or religious background by responding to their needs and interests. Accessible secondary education provides high-quality career counselling and lifelong learning programmes that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self-reliance in the world of work. Hence, it reduces skill shortages through the production of skilled manpower relevant to the needs of the labour market. It promotes and encourages scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service, forges and cements national unity, and supports international understanding and interaction.

Given the immense importance of quality school governance as explained above, it is very sad to observe that the level of corruption in Nigerian secondary school's governance can no longer allow school administrators to prepare students for useful living in the society and further into higher institutions. Lack of principal's clinical supervision on quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision, school organizational innovation, and learning outcome is what most stakeholders agitate for at the moment. Unfortunately, most school administrators cannot conduct teacher performance evaluations based on regular attendance, examine how teachers start and end classes with instructional materials, relate to students according to their psychological needs, use a variety of teaching and learning methods, involve all students in the learning process, ensure coordination between students and parents. Some school administrators cannot encourage demonstration supervision among teachers and students as a result of corrupt practices in the school. They hardly pay attention to school and student cleanliness, be involved in co-curricular activities, keep transparent maintenance of the accounting system.

However, with the involvement of state departments of education in monitoring school improvement efforts, supervisory responsibilities have increasingly encompassed the task at the higher end of this list. In turn, these responsibilities involve supervisors in much more complex, collaborative, and developmental efforts with teachers, rather than with the more strictly inspection responsibilities of an earlier time. Educational supervisors ensure that the educational institution operates efficiently and within the legal requirements and rules. Thus, all efforts made with respect to improving the quality of school governance have appeared fruitless.

The present situation of supervision in schools as reported by Ezekwesili (2007) showed there has been the bane of failure in secondary school educational policies in Nigeria. A system not supervised and evaluated is in dire need of collapse. When supervision is absent, it leads to a lack of communication, which leads to the indiscipline of students in school. Students will become rude to the teachers, principals and to one another, the low grade shall be recorded in their academics, crimes of various types shall be exhibited, absenteeism, lateness, talking in the classrooms, disrupting the activities in the classroom and others. Less supervision causes gross negligence and often the cause of low morale and low productivity amongst students.

Nnebedum and Akinfolarin (2017) investigated the relationship between principals' supervisory techniques in school governance and attainment of anti-corruption war in secondary schools in Ebonyi state. The findings of the study revealed among others that there was a high positive correlation between classroom observation techniques and the attainment of the anti-corruption war in secondary schools in Ebonyi State. It also revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' demonstration techniques in school governance and the attainment of the anti-corruption war in secondary schools in Ebonyi state. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that government should provide opportunity for principals to attend conferences, workshops, seminars and colloquiums on supervisory techniques at least once a year both nationally for more acquisition of skills and knowledge for effective instructional supervision in order to keep them at par in fighting corruption with their foreign counterparts.

Asiyai (2015) examined corruption in secondary schools' supervision with the aim of finding out the types/forms, effects, and measures for combating the menace. Findings revealed that the types of corruption prevalent in secondary school supervision are examination related, admission related, finance related, inspection related and sexual related. Each of these types of corruption has different forms of manifestations. The causes of corruption in secondary schools included greed and the desire to get rich quick. The study concluded by recommending among others that all stakeholders in secondary education should have a moral re-orientation and in order to help in sanitizing the universities and create a corruption free learning environment in the school system.

Okendu (2012) determined whether corruption in instructional processes and supervision have any measurable bearing on the academic performance of secondary school students in Delga Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. The results of the data analysis indicated that regular corrupt practices in instructional supervision have a significant bearing on students' performance because it negatively affects instructional process with educational planning and academic program planning of secondary schools in Delga. Recommendations were proffered based on the findings to improve the instructional process and instructional supervision strengthening capacities of education managers, inducting subject teachers and funding day secondary education.

The significance of the study will be seen in its acting as an inspiration for school administrators to be committed to corruption-free educational supervision among other potential benefits. This study may also be useful to secondary education who are the prime targets of efforts to provide skills, knowledge, and competencies for useful living within the society and for higher education for the students. The study is particularly important to educational supervisors and school administrators since their supervisory functions at the secondary schools are the prerequisites for quality education and attainment of anti-corruption education in the school system. This investigation wishes to contribute to the filling of the gaps and hence, bring additional knowledge to already existing literature.

Statement of the Problem

Despite several studies undertaken to solve the problem associated with the quality of school governance through instructional supervision, the problem of corruption and poor-quality instructional supervision in Abia state still persists due to the poor quality of supervisors among others. For one thing, supervision of instruction is intended to improve school performance and school failure is still the worry of most stakeholders. This nurtures all sorts of malpractices and makes it difficult for secondary schools to respond to the perceived needs of producing graduates who could eke out useful living in the society, and as well further to higher education.

To eliminate corrupt practices at the secondary level, the right kinds of principals are needed in school governance to employ clinical and demonstration supervisory techniques in order to inspire teachers and students with a desire for self-improvement, and raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, appreciate the dignity of labour, achieve excellence, and hence, channel the nation to the envisaged transformation. The principals in the state seem to spend more of their statutory hours on other administrative duties to the detriment of supervision. It is in light of this unpleasant situation that this study was set out to investigate the influence of principals' supervisory techniques in school governance and attainment of anti-corruption in secondary schools in Abia State.

Statement of null hypotheses

Two null hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant influence of principals' clinical supervision for combating corruption on the attainment of quality school governance
2. Principals' class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption does not significantly influence the attainment of quality school governance

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the survey research design. The area of the study was Abia State, Nigeria. The population of this study comprised 81 principals available in 81 public secondary schools in Aba education zone of Abia State. School principals are the subjects for this study but teachers were randomly selected at the ratio of 4:1 as respondents to assess principals' supervisory skills and school governance. Census sampling technique was employed in this study and the entire 81 principals were used for the study. Four (4) teachers from each of the 81 secondary schools were to assess their principals, giving rise to 344 teachers selected from a population of 1,829 teachers for this purpose.

An instrument titled: Principals' Supervisory Techniques for Combating Corruption and Attainment of Quality School Governance Questionnaire (PSTCCAQSGQ) was used for data collection. It was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A consisted of demographic variables. Section B consisted of 30 items based on the variables of the study. The Likert-4-point scale response option of very often, often, sometimes and never were used to measure the sub-variables of the independent variable. The research instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach alpha reliability technique. Reliability index of the instrument was .88, indicating that the instrument was reliable. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents in all the secondary schools. Collected data were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Analysis of variance was considered most appropriate due to the fact that, all the independent sub-variables were categorized into levels, and the measurement for all these levels were at the nominal scale of measurement. The dependent variable was measured continuously at the interval level. All these reasons fit the assumptions of one-way analysis of variance including the fact that data for the independent sub-variables were obtained from independent observations.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of principals' clinical supervision on quality school governance.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is principals' clinical technique of supervision categorized as low, average and high; while the dependent variable is quality school governance measured by three indices including instructional supervision, school records, learning environment, and the overall quality school governance (being a sum of the three indices). To test this hypothesis, the means of quality school governance and its sub-variables, as well as low, average and high levels of principals' clinical supervision were computed and compared using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results of the analysis is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: One-way analysis of variance of the influence of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption on quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision, school record keeping, and learning environment

Quality school governance	Clinical technique of supervision	N	Mean	SD	SE
Instructional supervision	Low	20	11.15	1.80	.12655
	Average	50	14.43	.51	.04287
	High	11	17.79	1.56	.12517
	Total	81	14.13	3.16	.14132
School record keeping	Low	20	17.27	3.79	.26631
	Average	50	17.64	2.89	.24304
	High	11	18.12	2.89	.24015
	Total	81	17.64	3.33	.14889

Learning Environment	Low	20	11.31	3.26	.22876	
	Average	50	12.37	3.21	.26920	
	High	11	12.55	3.64	.29236	
	Total	81	11.99	3.41	.15245	
Overall Quality school governance	Low	20	39.71	6.76	.47473	
	Average	50	44.41	4.96	.41612	
	High	11	48.46	5.46	.43882	
	Total	81	43.77	6.95	.31096	
School gov.	Source of var.	SS	DF	MS	F	Sig
Instructional supervision	Between groups	3915.110	2	1957.555	911.438*	.000
	Within groups	1067.440	96	2.148		
	Total	4982.550	98			
School record Keeping	Between groups	22.347	2	315.874	28.713*	.006
	Within groups	5508.853	96	11.001		
	Total	5531.200	98			
Learning Environment	Between groups	76.806	2	80.967	7.139*	.001
	Within groups	5722.192	96	11.342		
	Total	5798.998	98			
Overall school Governance	Between groups	80.1532	2	3409.088	97.910*	.000
	Within groups	24042.935	96	34.819		
	Total	24123.088	98			

Significant at .05, F critical = 3.02

The result in Table 1 showed the descriptive statistic summary of quality school governance based on principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption level in the sampled secondary schools. A close observation of Table 1 showed that when instructional supervision was considered, respondents who perceived the level of principals' clinical techniques of supervision for combating corruption to be high, had the highest quality of school governance in terms of instructional supervision ($t=17.79$), followed by those who perceived it as average ($t=14.43$) and lastly by those who perceived it as low ($t=11.15$).

When quality school governance in terms of school record keeping was considered, the result in Table 1 showed that respondents who perceived the level of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption to be high, had the highest mean of school record keeping ($t=18.12$), followed by those who perceived it to be average ($t=17.64$) and lastly by those who perceived it to be low ($t=17.27$). When quality school governance in terms of good learning environment was considered, the result in Table 1 also revealed that teachers who perceived the level of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption to be high, had the highest means score ($t=12.55$) followed by those who perceived it as average ($t=12.37$) and lastly by those perceived it to be low ($t=1.31$). When the overall quality of school governance was considered, the result in Table 1 showed that teachers who perceived the level of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption as high, had the highest mean score ($t=48.64$), followed by teachers who perceived it average ($t=44.44$) and lastly, by those who perceived it as low ($t=39.71$).

The hypothesis was tested with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The result of the analysis showed that there is a significant influence of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption on quality governance of secondary school in terms of instructional supervision ($F=911.438$; $p<.05$), school record keeping ($F=28.713$, $p<.05$); learning environment ($F=7.139$; $p<.05$) and overall quality school governance ($F=97.910$; $p<.05$). The null hypothesis that proposed a no significant influence of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption was rejected. This is because the calculated F-ratios of (911.43; 28.713; 71.139; 97.910) were found to be greater than the critical F-ratio, 3.02 at 0.5 alpha level with 2 and 98 degrees of freedom.

Given the significant F-ratio, a multiple comparison test analysis was conducted using Fisher's (LSD) to locate the source of difference. The result of the analysis was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Fisher's (LSD) multiple comparison test analysis of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption on quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision, school record keeping, and learning environment

Quality school governance	Clinical technique	Low (n=203)	Average (n=142)	High (n=155)
Instructional supervision	Low	11.13a	-369b	-6.659
	Average	-20.59*c	14.43	-3.359
	High	-42.59*	-19.72*	17.79
		MSW=2.148		
School record keeping	Low	17.27	-369b	.852
	Average	-1.02c	17.64	-482
	High	-2.41*c	1.25	18.12c
		MSW=11.001		
Learning Environment	Low	11.13a	-1.051b	
	Average	-2.85*c	12.37	-188
	High	-3.45**	-0.48*	12.55
		MSW=11.32		
Overall Quality school Governance	Low	39.71a	-4.722b	-8.750
	Average	-732*c	44.44	-4.028
	High	-3.90*	-5.88	48.46
		MSW=41.865		

Significant at 05.

- a. Group means are placed on the principal diagonal
- b. Difference between group means are placed above the diagonal
- c. Fishers LSD t-values are placed below the diagonal

Examination of the result presented in Table 2 showed that when quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision was considered, respondents who perceived the level of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption as high, had significantly higher mean difference than those who perceived it as low (MD = -42.59) and average (MD = -19.72). Other pair of comparison between average and low was also significant at .05 alpha level (MD = -20.59). This finding indicated that the higher the principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption, the higher the level of their quality of school governance in terms of instructional supervision.

When the quality of school governance in terms of school records keeping was considered, the result in Table 2 showed that teachers who perceived the level of principals' clinical technique of supervision to be high had a significantly higher mean score than teachers who perceived it to be low (MD =2.47). Other pairwise comparisons between average and low (t=1.25) were found to be insignificant. This finding means that when the principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption increases, accurate/updated school records also increases, hence encouraging quality school governance.

This finding indicated that teachers who perceived principals' clinical technique of supervision to be high, significantly had a higher level of quality of school governance in terms of school learning environment, than those that perceived it as low. When the overall quality school governance was considered, the result in Table 2 showed that, teachers who perceived the level of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption as high, had significantly higher mean difference

between them than those who perceived it as low (MD = -3.90) and average (MD = -5.88). Another pairwise comparison between average and low was found also to be significant (MD = -7.32). This finding implies that a high level of principals' clinical technique of supervision for combating corruption in those schools increased their overall quality school governance.

Hypothesis 2: Principals class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption does not significantly influence the quality school governance.

The independent variable in the hypothesis is principals class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption which is categorized as low, average and high. While the dependent variable is quality school governance measured by three indices of instructional supervision, school record keeping, and good learning environment. The null hypothesis was tested using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: One-way analysis of variance of the influence of principals' class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption on quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision, school record keeping, and learning environment.

Quality school governance	Class visitation techniques of supervision	N	Mean	SD	SE	
Instructional Supervision	Low	20	13.74	3.0	.400	
	Average	50	14.09	2.92	.488	
	High	11	14.72	13.39	.400	
	Total	81	14.13	3.16	.488	
School Recordkeeping	Low	20	14.63	2.50	.568	
	Average	50	14.35	0.48	.373	
	High	11	21.22	1.24	.456	
	Total	81	17.64	3.33	.373	
Learning environment	Low	20	11.25	3.32	.530	
	Average	50	12.19	2.72	.456	
	High	11	12.87	2.84	.720	
	Total	81	11.99	3.41	.312	
Overall school Governance	Low	20	39.62	3.41	.922	
	Average	50	44.69	4.51	.310	
	High	11	48.84	5.61	.126	
	Total	81	43.77	6.95	.310	
Quality of school governance	Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig.
Instructional Supervision	Between groups	85.504	2	42.752	4.339*	.014
	Within groups	4897.046	96	9.853		
	Total	4982.550	98			
School record keeping	Between groups	3938.995	2	1968.497	614.700*	.000
	Within groups	1592.205	96	3.204		
	Total	5531.200	98			
Learning Environment	Between groups	241.568	2	120.78410	.802*	.000
	Within groups	5798.998	96	11.342		
	Total	5798.998	98			
	Between groups	7630.209	2	3815.104	194.965*	.000

Overall school governance	Within Group Total	16492.879	96	33.185
		24123.088	98	

Significant at .05, F critical = 3.02

Examination of Table 3 showed that when quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision was considered, respondents who perceived the level of principals' class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption had the highest mean of quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision ($t=14.77$), followed by those who perceived it as average ($t=14.09$) and lastly by those who perceived it as low. When quality school governance in terms of school record keeping was considered, the result in Table 3 showed that respondents who perceived the level of principal's class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption as high, had the highest mean in terms of school record keeping ($t=21.20$), followed by those who perceived it be average ($t=18.35$) and lastly by those who perceived it as low ($t=14.63$).

When quality of school governance in terms of good learning environment was considered, the result in Table 3 showed that respondents who perceived the level of principal's class visitation technique of supervision for combating corruption to be high, had the highest mean quality school governance in terms of good learning environment ($t=12.87$), and lastly by those who perceived it to be low ($t=11.25$). When the overall quality school governance was considered, the result in Table 3 showed that the respondents who perceived it to be high had the highest mean score ($t=48.81$), followed by those who perceived it to be average ($t=44.69$) and lastly, by those who perceived it to be low ($t=39.62$).

Using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), the hypothesis was tested and the result of the analysis was presented in Table 3. The result of the analysis presented in Table 3 showed that there is a significant influence of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption in terms of instructional supervision ($F=4.339$; $p<.05$), school record keeping ($F=614.770$; $p<.05$), learning environment ($F=10.802$; $p<.05$) and overall quality school governance ($F=194.965$; $p<.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis that tentatively stated a no significant influence of principles' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption on quality school governance was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted consequently. This is because the calculated F-ratios of (4.339, 614.770, 10,802, 114.965) were found to be greater than the critical F-ratio of 3.02 given .05 level of significance and with 2 and 98 degrees of freedom. Given the significant F-ratio, a detailed multiple comparison test analysis was done using Fisher's LSD to locate the sources of difference. Table 4 presented the results of the analysis.

Table 4: Fisher's (LSD) multiple comparison test analysis of the influence of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption in terms of instructional supervision, school record keeping and learning environment.

Quality school governance	Class visitation techniques of supervision	Low (n=213)	Average (n=135)	High (n=152)
Instructional supervision	Low	13.74	-3.52b	-.980
	Average	-1.02c	14.408	-.628
	High	-2.94*	-1.69*	14.72
		MSW=9.853		
School record keeping	Low	14.63a	-3.721b	-6.583
	Average	18.90*c	18.35	-2.361
	High	34.64*	13.52*	21.22
		MSW=3.204		
Learning environment	Low	11.25a	-.944b	-1.626
	Average	-2.56*c	12.19	-.682

	High	-4.58*	-1.72*	12.87
		MSW=110182		
Overall Quality school governance	Low	39.62	-5.017	-9.189
	Average	-7.92*	44.64	-4.172
	High	-15.02*	-6.12*	48.81
		MSW=33.85		

Significant at .05

- a. Group means are placed on the principal diagonal
- b. Difference between group means are placed above the diagonal
- c. Fishers LSD t-values are placed below the diagonal

Examination of the results in Table 4 showed that when quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision was considered, respondents who perceived the level of principals' demonstration techniques of supervision for combating corruption as high had a significantly higher mean difference than those who perceived it as low (MD = -2.94). Another pairwise comparison between high and average (MD = -1.69), and between average and low (MD = 1.02) total quality of school governance were found to be insignificant. These findings indicated that higher level of principal' class visitation techniques of supervision produces higher quality school governance in terms of instructional supervision than low or average level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption.

When quality of school governance in terms of school record keeping was considered, the result in Table 4 showed that respondents who perceived the level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption as high had significantly higher mean scores in school record keeping than those who perceived it as low (MD=34.64) and average (MD=13.52). In the same vein, respondents who perceived the principals' class visitation technique of supervision as average has a significantly higher mean score than those who perceived it to be low (MD=18.90). This finding means that the higher the level of class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption, the higher the quality of school governance would be in terms of record keeping.

When the quality of school governance in terms of learning environment was considered, the result in Table 4 showed that the respondents who perceived the level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption as high, had a significantly higher mean score than those who perceived it as low (MD=4.58). Similarly, respondents who perceived it as average had a significantly higher mean score than those who perceived it as low (MD= -256). Another pairwise comparison was found to be insignificant (MD= -1.72). This finding indicated that a high level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption for teachers tantamount to high-quality school governance in terms of a good learning environment in secondary school.

When the overall quality school governance was considered, the result in Table 4 showed that respondents who perceived the level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption as high, had significantly higher mean score than those respondents who perceived the level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption as low (MD= -15.02) and average (MD= -6.12). Another pairwise comparison between average and low was also found to be significant (MD= -7.92). This finding indicates that a higher level of principals' class visitation techniques of supervision for combating corruption in the school increase not only teachers' credibility but also the school overall quality governance and vice versa.

Discussion of Findings

The result of data analysis indicated that there is an influence of principals' clinical technique of supervision in combating corruption and quality school governance in Abia education zone of Abia state. This implies that principals' regular observation of teacher instructional delivery in the classroom in terms of mastery of the subject matter, application of teaching strategies and aids, classroom management, and organization among others have a positive influence on school governance; hence, combating corruption. This finding supports the finding of Sule, Arop, and Alade (2012) which reported

that there was a significant influence of principals' classroom visitation/observation strategies influence on combating corruption for school quality governance.

Okendu (2012) also discovered that regular corrupt practices in instructional supervision have a significant bearing on students' performance because it negatively affects instructional process with educational planning and academic program planning of secondary schools in Delga. The finding implies that for the attainment of a corrupt-free school atmosphere, the principal must apply sustainable clinical and demonstration supervisory indices through practical discussion and work on a particular topic or subject has a positive influence on teachers' job performance.

The second finding of this study established that there was a significant influence of principals' class visitation techniques on quality school governance. Principals' class visitation or illustration of a concept provides an opportunity for teachers to discover new methods and ideas to be applied during instructional delivery in order to enhance their performance. This finding corroborates the finding of Nnebedum and Akinfolarin (2017) which revealed among others that there was a high positive correlation between classroom observation techniques and the attainment of anti-corruption war in secondary schools in Ebonyi State. It also revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' demonstration techniques in school governance and the attainment of the anti-corruption war in secondary schools in Ebonyi state.

The implication of this finding is that, regular instructional supervision using robust supervision strategies like checking of students' notebooks, classroom visitation/inspection by school administrators, checking teachers' lesson plan/notes and inspection of teacher's record keeping have significant influence on the manner in which the school administrators will govern and manage secondary schools in Aba education zone.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that there was a significant influence of principals' supervisory practices for combating corruption and attainment of quality school governance. Thus, regular observation and demonstration of supervision roles over teachers and students' and provision of the necessary professional guidance did positively influence the quality of school governance in terms of instructional supervision, school record keeping and good learning environment in public secondary schools.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The government at all levels should provide an opportunity for principals to attend conferences, workshops, to checkmate corrupt practices in the school system.
2. Principals should endeavor to regularly visit teachers' classroom instructional delivery and provide professional guidance and assistance to them where necessary.
3. Secondary school principals should adopt a clinical approach in the supervision of teachers and other activities in the school. This will improve the quality of school governance and reduce drastically, the level of corruption in schools.

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